

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE TRADITIONAL DURIAN CAKE PURCHASING BEHAVIOR OF VIETNAMESE CONSUMERS

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Abstract

Objective: This article researches the factors affecting the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers. **Theoretical Framework:** Base on The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) **Method:** By a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods, the research group indicates the degree of impact of factors influencing the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior. **Results and Discussion:** Among those, there are 3 factors showing a direct impact on “Traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers” at a 5% significance level. The perceived quality factor (CL) affects the Attitude towards traditional durian cake (TD) with an impact level of 0.852. The impact on traditional durian cake purchasing behavior, the Ethnocentrism factor (TVC) has the largest impact level with an impact level of 0.518; Attitude towards traditional durian cake (TD) has an impact level of 0.276; Perceived price has an impact level of 0.191. The Subjective norm factor (CCQ) is not statistically significant to conclude about the impact on “Traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers” (HV). **Research Implications** Thereby, the research group has offered some suggestions to promote the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake products.

Keywords: Factors, Impact, Purchasing Behavior, Traditional Durian Cake, Vietnam (SDG8).

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the cake market in Vietnam is constantly expanding due to the influx of cakes from many different countries. Despite this, traditional Vietnamese cakes (Vietnamese cakes) maintain an important role in the country’s cuisine.

Appearing from thousands of years ago, Vietnamese cakes have gone deep into the subconscious and are associated with every Vietnamese childhood memory. People often relate Vietnamese cakes with their simplicity, closeness, and familiarity. No matter where they go, names like: Banh da lon dau xanh, banh tam bi, banh xeo (pancake), banh khot... still leave a deep impression on the hearts of diners. Diverse and rich, Vietnamese cakes appear everywhere in the 3 regions of the country, playing an important role and promising to develop further in the future. (Thanh Tuyen, 2025)

According to the page Willflyforfood, Vietnam is one of the countries with the best cuisine in the world, especially traditional cakes (Hong Nhung, 2023). Initially, the first Vietnamese folk cakes were born very simple and rustic. Most cakes are wrapped in fresh banana leaves, coconut leaves, dong leaves, bamboo leaves, or cooked on jackfruit leaves, bamboo leaves, and lun leaves. In the past, to make cakes, our ancestors had to grind rice, grind glutinous rice, pound rice, knead dough, press cakes, shape cakes, bake cakes, and steam cakes... (Tuong Vy, 2019)

Nowadays, the South has over 100 types of traditional cakes with numerous different processing methods. Every year, the Southern folk cake festival is still held, gathering artisans, introducing, and widely promoting culinary cultural values and contributing to expanding the consumption market (Hong Dang, 2019). Meanwhile, the capital Hanoi and the northern provinces are famous for street food stalls, with countless traditional cakes. Banh bot loc, banh it tran... are typical traditional cakes of the Central region.

The consumption market for traditional Vietnamese cakes is mainly domestic. However, with the reality of deep integration, many international friends visiting Vietnam enjoy Vietnamese cakes and many companies have signed orders and exported Vietnamese cakes to other countries. Processing traditional Vietnamese food products and ensuring international quality is a new direction that many food businesses choose to promote exports (Nguyen Ngan, 2023). However, due to food hygiene and safety requirements, Vietnamese cakes do not have preservatives, which is also a difficulty for long-distance transportation.

Considered one of the largest durian suppliers to the world, by the end of October 2024, Vietnam had made over 3 billion USD from exporting durians (Tam An, 2024). Vietnam has taken advantage of this abundant source of raw materials to process many durian products such as: durian ice cream, grilled durian, durian smoothie, durian sticky rice and especially traditional durian cakes such as: Pia cake (mung bean cake with durian), durian stuffed buns, durian mooncakes, durian cream puffs, fried durian cakes... For example, in the case of Pia cake, Soc Trang province has increased the production capacity for processing Pia cakes at family businesses. The total investment of the project reached more than 3.9 billion VND, of which 1.5 billion came from national support (tapchicongthuong.vn, 2023). Thus, it can be seen that the trend of focusing and investing in the production of Pia cakes in particular and traditional durian cakes in general is to meet the needs of many different customer segments.

Realizing the potential of the traditional durian cake production industry at establishments, craft villages, and the trend of Vietnamese consumers' interest in traditional confectionery products, the research group decided to choose the topic of the article: Researching factors affecting the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers. The research article focuses on exploring and analyzing the level of impact of factors on the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of consumers. Based on the research results, the group proposes a number of solutions to promote the traditional durian cake consumption behavior of Vietnamese people; while providing directions to develop the traditional durian cake market in the future.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS AND RESEARCH OVERVIEW

2.1. *Concept and characteristics of traditional durian cake*

Based on the summaries and research from articles and websites introducing and promoting the image of traditional cakes in general and traditional durian cakes in particular, in this article, the concept of traditional cakes and traditional durian cakes is approached by the research group as follows:

- *Traditional cake*

Traditional cakes are cakes with long-standing origins, associated with the culture, customs, and culinary life of a region or country. These types of cakes are often made according to traditional recipes, using natural ingredients. Vietnam is a country with many types of traditional cakes associated with different regions.

- *Traditional durian cake*

Traditional Vietnamese durian cakes are cakes made from pure durian combined with other natural ingredients, originating from a long time ago and popular in Vietnamese culinary culture. These types of cakes are often made by hand or semi-industrially, retaining the characteristic flavor of durian, and are often used on holidays, Tet, or as gifts.

- *Characteristics of traditional Vietnamese durian cake*

- + **Characteristic flavor:** Traditional Vietnamese durian cakes have the rich, creamy, sweet aroma of durian, either mildly sweet or intensely sweet depending on the specific recipe. Some traditional durian cakes can be combined with other ingredients such as salted egg, mung beans, and cheese...
- + **Natural ingredients:** The crust of traditional durian cakes can be made from various types of wheat flour, glutinous rice flour, egg flour... helping the cake to be soft or crispy depending on the type. In addition, traditional durian cakes do not use preservatives or minimize them to preserve the original flavor.
- + **Diverse forms:** Depending on the region and processing method, traditional durian cakes have many different designs and textures.
- + **Handmade processing:** Traditional durian cakes are often made using manual or semi-industrial methods to preserve the original flavor and have high freshness.
- + **Cultural value:** Often used as a form of gift on special, solemn occasions or in meetings to show sophistication in cuisine.

2.2. *Consumer behavior theory*

Consumer behavior is the actions and decisions that individuals or households make when they select, purchase, use, and dispose of a product or service (Bhat. Adi, 2021). This behavior integrates ideas from many scientific fields including psychology, biology, chemistry and economics. It relies on psychological principles to understand how

personal motivations, perceptions and attitudes shape consumer purchasing decisions. Biological factors such as physiological needs and sensory experiences also play a role in influencing consumer behavior. Economic theory helps explain how consumers allocate limited resources among competing needs, guiding businesses in pricing and product positioning strategies (Radu.V, 2023).

Purchase Intention. Purchase intention is the willingness of a customer to buy a specific product or use a specific service. Purchase intention is a variable dependent on many external and internal factors. Purchase intention is a measure of a respondent's attitude towards purchasing or using a service (MBA Skool Team, 2021). By unlocking the mysterious power of purchase intention, companies can understand customer desires and shopping habits. With this information, companies can design targeted advertising campaigns and marketing messages to drive sales and strengthen customer loyalty (Bhasin. H, 2023).

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) model by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) focuses on consumer behavior and determining their behavioral intentions, where behavioral intention is partly influenced by attitudes towards the behavior and partly by subjective norms (the influence of others also leads to their attitudes). This model predicts and explains the tendency to perform a behavior by examining consumers' attitudes towards the behavior, rather than simply their attitudes towards the product or service.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is a development and improvement of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), and is a commonly used theory when wanting to predict a specific behavior of any individual, which can be the behavior of choosing to buy products or services... The factors affecting the decision are personal attitudes and subjective norms. In which, personal attitude is measured by beliefs and evaluations of the consequences of that behavior. Ajzen. I (1991) defines subjective norms as the perception of influential people who think that the individual should or should not perform a certain behavior. The Theory of Planned Behavior also adds a third factor, perceived behavioral control. Perceived behavioral control is an individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to perform a behavior (related to the availability of necessary resources, knowledge, and opportunities to apply).

2.3. Ethnocentrism

The theory of ethnocentrism refers to the consumption of products with national cultural identities. With the increase of globalization and the development of competition in the field of international products and services, consumers are increasingly concerned about their national cultural identity. These national sentiments are reflected in consumer behavior through a preference for domestic consumer products – ethnocentric orientation (Visa. I, Faihurst. A, 1999). Sumner. G. A (1906) defines ethnocentrism as the view of members of the same group as the center of everything, while all views of other groups are considered unimportant. It can be seen that ethnocentrism refers to the psychological

tendency of individuals to evaluate the value of other groups/ethnicities lower than their own group/ethnicity, based on the perspective of their own group/ethnicity. Inheriting from Summer (1906), Shimp and Sharma (1987) developed the concept of consumer ethnocentrism theory (CET). This is the unique economic form of ethnocentrism, capturing consumer beliefs about the ethics and rationality of foreign consumption (in the US context). To date, ethnocentrism remains the most used concept to explain the phenomenon of consumer preference for domestic goods due to product quality factors, anti-foreign import views... (Klein, J.G & et al, 1998). Nguyen Bao Ngoc (2019) argues that people with consumer ethnocentrism distinguish between products of internal groups and external groups, tend to prefer domestic consumption and avoid buying foreign products due to ethnic reasons. Conversely, consumers without ethnocentrism often evaluate products based on price, quality and other characteristics of the products they are interested in. Thus, consumer ethnocentrism increases domestic consumption.

2.4. Research overview

Research on durian cakes in general and traditional durian cakes in particular is a topic that has not been approached comprehensively and extensively. Although traditional durian cakes are specialties of some localities, and carry many important meanings and roles in people's lives and the traditional confectionery market. However, there are not many empirical studies on traditional durian cakes. Most studies focus on analyzing the current situation of the traditional cake market. In fact, only a few studies analyze the development potential of durian in general and traditional durian cakes in particular, studies focus on detailed analysis of production and processing of products, confectionery market from durian, durian tree development prospects.... Research by Hoang Manh Cuong, et al (2021) on an overview of durian production and consumption in Vietnam and some countries in the region, shows the potential of durian products produced in Vietnam and some other countries such as China, Thailand... In addition, research by Do Thi Huong (2021) also shows the development potential of the durian market in general and durian processed products including confectionery, durian powder, durian pate... based on the characteristics, strengths and development opportunities of this fruit.

Besides, some empirical studies show the factors affecting the purchase behavior of confectionery in particular and some Vietnamese domestic products and foods and other countries around the world in general of consumers.

Research by Vuong Quoc Duy (2014) on the factors affecting the consumption of Pia cakes in Soc Trang shows the factors including: price, product utility, access methods, advertising, product information, product safety, product convenience, product quality, perceived impact on consumer behavior. In which, the study emphasizes the importance of quality, food hygiene and safety issues. Research by Phan Thanh Nam and Ngo Chi Thanh (2024) on the factors affecting the purchase behavior of domestic confectionery of Vietnamese people and the willingness of consumers to support this item. The research results show 5 factors affecting the purchase behavior of domestic confectionery including: Brand reputation, perceived quality, price, promotion and subjective norms; besides, the distribution factor is included in the analysis model but the results show no

impact on the purchase behavior of domestic confectionery of consumers. At the same time, the study proposes solutions based on the research results to promote the purchase behavior of confectionery of Vietnamese brands, thereby enhancing the competitiveness of businesses in the international arena. Research by Nguyen Thi Van Anh & et al (2022) on the factors affecting the purchase intention of traditional Ao Dai of Vietnamese Gen Z. The study analyzes the factors including: Attitude towards the product, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, ethnocentrism to consider the level of impact of factors on the purchase intention of traditional Vietnamese Ao Dai. The research results show that the perceived behavioral control factor has the greatest impact on the purchase intention of traditional Ao Dai. Based on the research results, the article proposes specific solutions to promote the purchase behavior of traditional Ao Dai, raise awareness of young people in using products as an act of expressing patriotism and national spirit.

Research by Tran Thi Tuan Anh & et al (2023) on the factors affecting the purchase intention and behavior of powdered milk of consumers - the moderating role of ethnocentrism. The article focuses on analyzing the factors affecting powdered milk purchase behavior. The research results show that the perceived behavioral control factor and monthly income have a direct impact on purchase behavior. Perceived quality, perceived price, behavioral attitude and ethnocentrism all affect consumer purchase behavior through purchase intention. However, the study did not find the influence of social influence and perceived behavioral control factors on the purchase intention of the survey subjects. Research by Tran Kim Dung (2015) on the factors affecting the behavioral intention of consumers in the Da Nang market for domestic confectionery products. The results show that the factors: perceived cost, perceived quality and domestic purchase intention have an impact on purchase behavior. In which, the perceived value factor including perceived cost and perceived quality has a great impact on the behavioral intention of consumers. At the same time, the study also shows that the perceived value factor accompanied by a suitable selling price is the leading factor affecting the behavioral intention of consumers in the Da Nang market. Lam Ngoc Thuy (2021) factors affecting the purchase intention of domestic fashion clothing of young people in Lam Dong province. The linear structural model is used to test the hypotheses by analyzing data from 251 consumers. The results show that the factors "Subjective Norms", "Attitude towards the product", "Ethnocentrism", "Perceived quality", "Emotional value", "Interest in clothing", "Social media communication" proposed in the research model have an impact on "Purchase intention of domestic fashion brands of young people".

The "ethnocentrism" factor is a characteristic factor and is no longer unfamiliar in studies on consumer behavior in developed countries. In Vietnam and developing countries, this factor has recently been mentioned in consumer behavior studies. Research on "ethnocentrism" of young people in the Central market shows that young people in the Central region have consumer ethnocentrism, however, the level of consumer ethnocentrism is not high. In addition, consumer ethnocentrism also changes depending on the type of product, specifically, young people in the Central region have higher ethnocentrism in products that are Vietnam's advantages, local and traditional products

such as fruits, clothes, handicrafts Ngo Thi Khue Thu (2015). Research by Le Nguyen Hau, Tran Truc Quynh and Le Duc Anh (2011) explores the role of consumer ethnocentrism, perceived quality and perceived price on the willingness to buy domestic goods (ready-made clothes) of Vietnamese consumers. The research results show that perceived price and ethnocentrism have a positive and direct impact, while perceived quality has an indirect impact on the willingness to buy domestic goods of consumers. Perceived quality and ethnocentrism also have a positive impact on perceived price. Research by Tran Thi Tuan Anh & et al (2023) shows that ethnocentrism plays an important role in moderating the relationship between perceived quality and purchase intention, as well as the relationship between attitude and purchase intention. Research by Pham Thi Be Loan and Bui Thanh Huan (2012) on the purchase behavior of children's tonics produced in the country of consumers, refers to the factors of ethnocentrism, perceived value, domestic goods belief. The article studies the linear structural model between the factors (1) ethnocentrism, (2) perceived value, (3) domestic goods belief and behavioral intention in the field of children's tonics. Most studies show the "ethnocentrism" factor has a positive impact on the purchase behavior of "traditional", "domestic" products or specialties, characteristics of regions. However, research by Tran Kim Dung (2015) shows that the ethnocentrism factor has no impact, showing that consumers are gradually integrating and the attitude of buying foreign goods is no longer criticized as before.

3. RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESES, RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research model and hypotheses

Based on the theoretical overview, the overview of related studies, and the characteristics of traditional durian cake products, the research group proposes a research model with the factors included in the model being "Perceived Quality" affecting "Attitude towards traditional durian cake", the factors "Attitude towards traditional durian cake", "Subjective Norms", "Perceived Price", "Ethnocentrism" affecting "Traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers".

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis H1: Perceived quality (CL) has a positive correlation impact on Attitude towards traditional Vietnamese durian cake (TD)

Hypothesis H2: Attitude towards traditional durian cake (TD) has a positive correlation impact on traditional Vietnamese durian cake purchasing behavior (HV)

Hypothesis H3: Subjective Norms (CCQ) has a positive correlation impact on traditional Vietnamese durian cake purchasing behavior (HV)

Hypothesis H4: Perceived Price (GC) has a positive correlation impact on traditional Vietnamese durian cake purchasing behavior (HV)

Hypothesis H5: Ethnocentrism (TVC) has a positive correlation impact on traditional Vietnamese durian cake purchasing behavior (HV)

Proposed Research Model:

Figure 1: Proposed research model

Research measurement scale specified by Table 1

Table 1: Basis for variable formation and factor measurement scale in the model

No.	Code	Observed Variable	Reference Source
I	CL	Perceived quality	
1	CL1	Traditional durian cake has a characteristic flavor	Phan Thanh Nam and Ngo Chi Thanh (2024); Le Nguyen Hau, Tran Truc Quynh, and Le Duc Anh (2011); Tran Thi Tuan Anh et al. (2023)
2	CL2	Traditional durian cake is good for health	
3	CL3	Traditional durian cake has a delicious flavor	
4	CL4	Traditional durian cake has a natural origin, safe for health	
5	CL5	Traditional durian cake has a variety of types	
II	TD	Attitude	
6	TD1	I like traditional Vietnamese durian cake	Lam Ngoc Thuy (2021); Tran Thi Tuan Anh et al. (2023)
7	TD2	I am attracted to the flavor of traditional durian cake	
8	TD3	I am excited when mentioning traditional durian cake	
9	TD4	Enjoying traditional durian cake brings me many benefits	
III	CCQ	Subjective norms	
10	CCQ1	People around me buy traditional durian cake	Lam Ngoc Thuy (2021); Phan Trung Nam (2013); Phan Thanh Nam and Ngo Chi Thanh (2024); Tran Thi Tuan Anh et al. (2023)
11	CCQ2	People around me advise me to buy traditional durian cake	
12	CCQ3	There is a lot of information about traditional durian cake on current media	
13	CCQ4	Traditional durian cake is promoted by influential people	
IV	TVC	Ethnocentrism	
14	TVC1	Vietnamese people should buy traditional durian cake	Tran Kim Dung (2015); Le Nguyen Hau, Tran Truc Quynh, and Le Duc Anh (2011); Tran Thi Tuan Anh et al. (2023)
15	TVC2	Buying traditional durian cake makes me feel happy	
16	TVC3	I will buy traditional durian cake during traditional Tet holidays	
17	TVC4	Enjoying traditional durian cake makes me feel proud of national cuisine	

V	GC	Perceived price	
18	GC1	The price of traditional durian cake is stable in the market	Phan Thanh Nam and Ngo Chi Thanh (2024); Le Nguyen Hau, Tran Truc Quynh, and Le Duc Anh (2011); Tran Thi Tuan Anh et al. (2023)
19	GC2	Traditional durian cake has many price ranges to choose from	
20	GC3	The price of traditional durian cake is suitable for my income	
21	GC4	The price of traditional durian cake is commensurate with its quality	
VI	HV	Traditional durian cake purchasing behavior	
22	HV1	Buying traditional durian cake is the right decision	Phan Thanh Nam and Ngo Chi Thanh (2024); Le Nguyen Hau, Tran Truc Quynh, and Le Duc Anh (2011); Tran Thi Tuan Anh et al. (2023)
23	HV2	Buying traditional durian cake is a good thing to do	
24	HV3	I will recommend traditional durian cake to others	
25	HV4	I will continue to buy traditional durian cake in the future	

Source: *Synthesis and proposal by the research team.*

3.2. Research methodology

Data collection methods

Based on the theoretical and research overview of the factors affecting consumer behavior in general, the purchase behavior of domestic products, and traditional products, studies on durian cakes, the research group built a proposed model, built a survey questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire is built with a 5-point Likert scale, with:

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

After building the survey questionnaire, the research group conducted a random test survey of 10 consumers, the preliminary survey results showed that the opinions agreed with the factors included in the model. Based on the preliminary survey, the research group conducted a large-scale survey via Google Forms with the target audience of consumers in Vietnam via the link (<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1dJlaN7H-6zUM4vpH6ilpdkZ1a9GO2MEp6fcO9ki6QIQ/preview>).

Due to time and resource constraints for the survey, the author used the convenience sampling method. The sample size is determined according to Comrey and Lee's rule (1992), while referring to Hoang Trong & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc's rule (2005). With 25 observed variables to be factor analyzed, the minimum number of samples required is $25 \times 5 = 125$ observed samples. From the perspective of collecting as many observed samples as possible to ensure the stability of measurement, based on the ability to collect

samples, the research group decided to choose the number of survey questionnaires > 300. In fact, the number of survey questionnaires collected was 330, of which 195 questionnaires were from people who had purchased traditional durian cakes (ensuring greater than 125 questionnaires) were included in the analysis of influencing factors. The research data after collection will be cleaned and analyzed with the support of SMARTPLS software with analytical techniques.

Data processing methods

The structural regression equation has the general form:

$$TD = a*CL$$

$$HV = b*TD + c*CCQ + d*GC + e*TVC$$

Quantitative research methods are conducted to process research data collected from surveys of Vietnamese consumers on factors affecting Vietnamese traditional cake purchase behavior. SMARTPLS software is used to test hypotheses and assess the impact of factors.

Step 1: Evaluate the measurement model

Evaluate the measurement model based on considering the values of observed variable quality (outer loadings), scale reliability (Cronbach’s Alpha), convergence and discriminant validity.

Step 2: Evaluate the structural model

After evaluating the measurement model to meet the requirements, evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, path coefficient, total coefficient determining R squared, impact coefficient f squared.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Description of survey participants

The survey link received 330 responses, with the following details regarding gender, occupation, and age:

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of survey participants

	Count	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	97	29,39
Female	218	66,06
Prefer not to specify	15	4,55
Occupation status		
Student	259	78,48
Employed	68	20,61
Retired	3	0,91
Area of residence		
Urban	304	92,1

Rural	26	7,88
Monthly income		
No income	139	42,12
Under 5 million VND	102	30,91
5 to under 10 million VND	30	9,1
10 to under 20 million VND	29	8,8
20 to under 50 million VND	24	7,3
50 million VND and above	6	1,77
Awareness of traditional durian cake		
Yes	272	82,42
No	58	17,58
Purchased traditional durian cake (among those aware)		
Yes (Previously)	195	71,96
No	76	28,04

Source: Survey results

Consumers participating in the survey were predominantly female, with a significantly higher percentage than males. Specifically, the number of male consumers participating in the survey was only about 29.39% (97 people), while the percentage of female consumers was 66.06% (218 people). The remaining 15 consumers (accounting for 4.55%) did not wish to specify their gender. Regarding the characteristics of the survey participants, the majority of consumers were students (accounting for 78.48% of the total number of survey participants), in addition, 68 survey participants were employed (accounting for about 20.61%) and only 3 survey participants were retired. This shows that most students have a tendency and behavior to buy traditional durian cakes. Regarding the area of residence, consumers participating in the survey were mainly in urban areas (92.12%), besides there were 26 people in rural areas. In terms of monthly income, the majority of survey participants had no income or had an income of less than 5 million VND. The reason stems from the characteristics of the survey participants, most of whom are students, so they have no or low income. Specifically, 42.12% of the survey participants had no income; 30.91% had an income of less than 5 million VND. The number of people with monthly income from 5 to under 10 million; from 10 to under 20 million; from 20 to under 50 million were all in the range of 9-10%, without too much difference. Survey participants with income from 50 million or more accounted for about 1.77% (6 people).

4.2. Assessing the purchasing trend of traditional durian cake among Vietnamese consumers

When asked about their awareness of traditional durian cake, 272 survey participants answered that they were aware (accounting for approximately 82.42%); among those who were aware of traditional durian cake, 71.96% of the people had purchased durian cake. The remaining 76 people (accounting for approximately 28.04% of the survey participants) had never purchased durian cake. The reasons why they had never purchased traditional durian cake are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Reasons for not purchasing traditional durian cake

Source: Survey results

Of the 272 people aware of traditional durian cake, 76 people have never purchased or do not purchase traditional durian cake. The majority stated that the reason stemmed from the lack of many stores selling traditional durian cake (29 opinions); in addition, 21 opinions stated that they did not like traditional durian cake. Furthermore, other opinions also indicated that the characteristic durian smell, traditional durian cake being too fatty or the high price and difficulty in preserving durian cake. These are the barriers that prevent consumers from buying or never having the intention to buy traditional durian cake.

Figure 3: Purpose of purchasing traditional durian cake

Source: Survey result

Among the 195 surveyed individuals who have purchased traditional durian cake, the majority bought it to enjoy the flavor of traditional durian cake (174 opinions); additionally, 77 opinions also indicated that they bought traditional durian cake not only to enjoy but also to give as gifts to those around them or on special occasions.

Figure 4: Reasons for purchasing traditional durian cake

Source: Survey result

When asked about the reasons consumers decide to buy traditional durian cake, most of them want to enjoy the flavor of traditional durian cake (145 opinions); 110 opinions believe they buy traditional durian cake because of its distinctive delicious flavor. Additionally, some reasons why consumers buy traditional durian cakes also stem from the desire to support traditional Vietnamese products (74 opinions) and because durian cakes are suitable gifts (47 opinions).

Figure 5: Occasions for purchasing traditional durian cake

Source: Survey result

Regarding the occasions for buying traditional durian cakes, the majority of consumers buy traditional durian cakes on regular, everyday occasions (165 opinions); only 64 opinions indicated that they buy traditional durian cakes during the Tet holidays.

This shows that consumers nowadays do not place much importance on the occasion to buy traditional durian cakes; they can purchase them during festive occasions for gifting purposes or simply buy them on regular days to enjoy....

Figure 6: Type of traditional durian cake consumers want to purchase

Source: Survey result

Regarding the type of traditional durian cake that consumers prefer to purchase, a significant portion of the survey participants expressed a preference for partially stylized traditional durian cakes, such as those with reduced sweetness or combined with other flavors to enhance flavor diversity (109 opinions).

This preference is attributed to the current “eat clean” trend and the influx of various cakes from different countries with distinctive and appealing flavors. Consequently, consumers tend to favor durian cakes that retain traditional characteristics while incorporating some innovation and reduced sweetness.

Conversely, a considerable number of respondents still prefer the original traditional durian cake (80 opinions), as they appreciate the familiar traditional flavor. Furthermore, 74 respondents indicated a preference for mass-produced traditional durian cakes, citing cost-effectiveness and accessibility as reasons for their choice.

On the other hand, some respondents expressed a preference for handmade traditional durian cakes from craft villages, possibly due to the perception that handmade cakes retain the authentic traditional characteristics that mass-produced cakes may lack.

Figure 7: Consumer channels for purchasing traditional durian cakes

Source: Survey result

Regarding the purchasing channels for traditional durian cakes among consumers, the majority of respondents expressed a preference for purchasing directly from grocery stores and supermarkets (160 opinions). 66 respondents indicated a desire to purchase traditional durian cakes through social media platforms, online channels, and e-commerce platforms. 36 respondents expressed a preference for purchasing directly from craft villages and workshops that produce traditional durian cakes.

4.3. Model testing results

Assessment of the quality of observed variables in the measurement model

The research team conducted a model analysis, and the quality of the observed variables was evaluated using outer loadings. The outer loadings of the observed variables influencing the model are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Outer loadings of factors affecting the purchase behavior of traditional durian cakes among Vietnamese consumers

	CCQ	CL	GC	HV	TD_	TVC
CCQ1	0.889					
CCQ2	0.920					
CCQ3	0.894					
CCQ4	0.895					
CL1		0.856				
CL2		0.803				
CL3		0.881				

CL4		0.883				
CL5		0.843				
GC1			0.885			
GC2			0.881			
GC3			0.876			
GC4			0.898			
HV1				0.889		
HV2				0.903		
HV3				0.910		
HV4				0.877		
TD2					0.906	
TD3					0.907	
TD4					0.867	
TVC1						0.876
TVC2						0.885
TVC3						0.864
TVC4						0.903
TD1					0.894	

Source: Model testing results by the research team

The results presented in Table 3 indicate that the outer loadings of all the indicators measuring the constructs related to factors influencing Vietnamese consumers' purchase behavior toward traditional durian cakes are greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2016), suggesting that the observed variables are statistically significant and contribute meaningfully to their respective constructs.

Assessment of scale reliability

The reliability of the measurement scales for the constructs affecting the purchase behavior of Vietnamese consumers toward traditional durian cakes was evaluated using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Two key indicators were employed to assess internal consistency reliability: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 4: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability of factors influencing the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumer

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CCQ	0.921	0.923	0.944	0.809
CL	0.907	0.910	0.931	0.729
GC	0.908	0.910	0.935	0.784
HV	0.917	0.917	0.941	0.801
TD	0.916	0.916	0.941	0.798
TVC	0.905	0.909	0.933	0.778

Source: Model testing results by the research team

According to Table 4, the results of the reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for each construct are as follows: Subjective norms (CCQ) = 0.921; Perceived quality (CL) = 0.907; Perceived price (GC) = 0.908; Traditional durian cake purchase

behavior (HV) = 0.917; Attitude toward traditional durian cake (ATT) = 0.916; and Consumer ethnocentrism (TVC) = 0.905. All values exceed the recommended threshold of 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012), indicating that the scales meet the reliability criterion. None of the indicators violated the removal rule, thus no items were excluded, and all constructs are considered acceptable in terms of internal consistency reliability. The Composite Reliability (CR) values for all constructs also exceed 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) (Table 4). Therefore, the measurement scales demonstrate strong reliability, are analytically meaningful, and are retained for subsequent factor analysis.

Convergence

According to the data analysis results in Table 4, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of the factors are as follows: Subjective Norms (CCQ) is 0.809; Perceived Quality (CL) is 0.729; Perceived Price (GC) is 0.784; Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior (HV) is 0.801; Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake (TD) is 0.798; Ethnocentrism (TVC) is 0.778. Thus, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of all variables is > 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), indicating that the model satisfies the convergence criteria.

Discriminant validity

The results in Table 5 regarding the Fornell-Larcker criteria for the research model on factors affecting: Subjective norms (CCQ); Perceived Quality (CL); Perceived Price (GC); Traditional durian cake purchasing behavior (HV); Attitude towards traditional durian cake (TD); Ethnocentrism (TVC) all demonstrate discriminant validity. This is because all square root AVE values on the diagonal are higher than their off-diagonal values. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, both the cross-loading and Fornell-Larcker criteria are satisfied.

Table 5: Fornell-Larcker criterion of the research model on factors influencing the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumer

	CCQ	CL	GC	HV	TD_	TVC
CCQ	0.900					
CL	0.620	0.854				
GC	0.653	0.814	0.885			
HV	0.639	0.801	0.807	0.895		
TD_	0.688	0.852	0.799	0.815	0.893	
TVC	0.661	0.827	0.786	0.869	0.771	0.882

Source: Model testing results by the research team

f² effect size

The f² effect size represents the magnitude of the impact of a construct (factor) when it is removed from the model. The f² values correspond to 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, representing small, medium, and large effect sizes (Cohen, 1988) of the exogenous variable. If the effect size is < 0.02, it is considered to have no effect.

Table 6: Summary of f^2 values

	CCQ	CL	GC	HV	TD	TVC
CCQ				0.001		
CL					2.656	
GC				0.057		
HV						
TD				0.119		
TVC				0.459		

Source: Model testing results by the research team

In this model, as shown in Table 6, the factors exhibit the following effects: Perceived Quality (CL) has a significant effect on Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake (TD) with a value of 2.656; Ethnocentrism (TVC) has a substantial effect on Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior of Vietnamese consumers (HV) with a value of 0.459; Perceived Price (GC) and Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake (TD) have a moderate effect on Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior, with values of 0.057 and 0.119, respectively; however, the f^2 value of the CCQ variable is less than 0.02, indicating that CCQ has no effect on HV.

4.3.2. Results of assessing the impact level using the structural model

Evaluation of impact relationships

The relationships and impact levels of the factors affecting the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers, as determined by SMARTPLS, are illustrated in Image 2.

Figure 8: Factors influencing the traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers

Source: SMARTPLS model testing results by the research team

The results of the Bootstrap analysis for evaluating impact relationships are presented in Table 7. Accordingly, the variables Perceived Quality (CL) and Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake (TD) have P Values < 0.05, indicating that the Perceived Quality variable has sufficient statistical significance to represent a positive relationship with TD. The variables Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake (TD), Perceived Price (GC), and Ethnocentrism (TVC) have P Values < 0.05; this indicates that these factors have sufficient statistical significance to represent a positive impact relationship with Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior (HV). (*Hypotheses H1, H2, H4, and H5 are accepted*).

The Subjective Norms (CCQ) factor has a P Value > 0.05, indicating that this factor does not have sufficient statistical significance to represent a relationship with the Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior of Vietnamese consumers (*Hypothesis H3 is not accepted*).

Table 7: Path coefficients of the structural model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
CCQ -> HV	-0.017	-0.013	0.049	0.354	0.724
CL -> TD	0.852	0.851	0.026	32.383	0.000
GC -> HV	0.191	0.195	0.079	2.416	0.016
TD -> HV	0.276	0.274	0.081	3.391	0.001
TVC -> HV	0.518	0.514	0.059	8.832	0.000

Source: SMARTPLS model testing results by the research team

The verification results in Table 7 show that, at a 95% confidence level, Perceived Quality (CL) affects Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake (TD) with an impact level of 0.852. Among the factors directly impacting Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior, Ethnocentrism (TVC) has the largest impact level of 0.518; Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake (TD) has an impact level of 0.276; and Perceived Price (GC) has an impact level of 0.191 on “Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior of Vietnamese consumers”.

The Subjective Norms (CCQ) factor does not have sufficient statistical significance to conclude about its impact on the dependent variable “Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior of Vietnamese consumers” (HV).

Thus, we have the following regression equations:

$$TD = 0.852 * CL$$

$$HV = 0.518 * TVC + 0.276 * TD + 0.191 * GC$$

Evaluation of the Overall Coefficient of Determination R² (R-squared)

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis provide the R² value, which reflects the degree of explanation of the independent variables for the dependent variable. The R² value measures the overall coefficient of determination, which is an index to measure the goodness of fit of the data to the model (the explanatory power of the model). According

to Hair et al. (2016), R-squared values of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25 are considered substantial, moderate, and weak, respectively.

Table 8: Coefficients of determination (R Square) of independent variables on the dependent variable

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
HV	0.818	0.814
TD_	0.726	0.725

Source: Model testing results by the research team

The results from Table 8 indicate that for the dependent variable HV, R^2 is 0.818 and adjusted R^2 is 0.814. This means that the independent variables in the model explain 81.8% of the “Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior of Vietnamese consumers”. Similarly, for the dependent variable TD, R^2 is 0.726 and adjusted R^2 is 0.725, meaning that the Perceived Quality (CL) variable can explain 72.6% of the “Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake”.

Assessment of the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)

The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) indicates the goodness of fit of the research model. According to Hu & Bentler (1999), a well-fitting model typically has an SRMR value less than 0.08.

Table 9: Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) Index

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.060	0.071

Source: Model testing results by the research team

The research results for SRMR in Table 9 show that SRMR is less than 0.08. Therefore, this model is suitable for data analysis.

5. DISCUSSION

The research results indicate that Perceived quality has a positive impact on Attitude towards Traditional Durian Cake. This result is consistent with the research previously synthesized and analyzed by the group. Furthermore, factors including Attitude towards traditional durian cake, Ethnocentrism, and Perceived price exhibit a positive correlation with traditional durian cake purchasing behavior, which aligns with previous research. However, in this study, the Subjective Norms factor did not have sufficient statistical significance to demonstrate a relationship with consumer purchasing behavior, which contradicts some prior research.

To explain this discrepancy, it can be observed that while social influence on consumer behavior exists, its impact varies depending on the product type, item, and the surveyed customer demographics. In the context of this study, which examines the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers regarding traditional durian cake, consumers may prioritize product quality and other factors, emphasizing direct experience over influence

from others. Therefore, from a practical standpoint, the research results are considered appropriate. Based on the research findings, among the four factors examined, three exhibited a statistically significant impact (at the 5% level) on “Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior of Vietnamese Consumers”. Consequently, the research team assessed the mean values of these factors and proposed the following suggestions:

Ethnocentrism factor: The four measurement items: Vietnamese people should buy traditional durian cake (TVC1); Buying traditional durian cake makes me feel happy (TVC2); I will buy traditional durian cake during traditional Tet holidays (TVC3); and Enjoying traditional durian cake makes me feel proud of national cuisine (TVC4) were all rated “Agree” by consumers.

This indicates that ethnocentrism has a significant impact on the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers. Notably, durian is a characteristic fruit of Vietnam, and traditional durian cake is a unique culinary feature of certain regions. Consumers tend to purchase domestic and traditional products to support the development of domestic industries.

When they perceive that buying traditional durian cake contributes to domestic product consumption and expresses patriotism, they feel happy to purchase it for personal enjoyment or as gifts, demonstrating national pride. Therefore, the research team suggests that craft villages and production workshops should innovate in product design and flavor to enhance brand recognition.

For example, artisans can incorporate traditional Vietnamese patterns or images onto products or packaging. Additionally, distribution and promotional channels can create programs and campaigns that associate traditional durian cake with historical or cultural events and folklore, thereby celebrating the beauty of traditional durian cake and promoting its purchase among Vietnamese consumers.

Figure 9: Mean value of the “Consumer Ethnocentrism” factor

Source: Survey results

Attitude towards traditional durian cake: The four measurement items: I like traditional Vietnamese durian cake (TD1); I am attracted to the flavor of traditional durian cake (TD2); I am excited when mentioning traditional durian cake (TD3); and Enjoying traditional durian cake brings me many benefits (TD4) were all rated “Agree” by the survey participants. This indicates that attitude towards traditional durian cake has a significant impact on consumers’ decision to purchase it. Traditional durian cake is no longer unfamiliar to people, especially those born in regions where this cake is a specialty. Traditional durian cake often has the characteristic flavor of durian fruit. Therefore, when consumers have a tendency to like durian cake, or like the flavor and benefits it brings, they will tend to purchase traditional durian cake more frequently. Consequently, the research team suggests that traditional durian cake craft villages or mass-production facilities should actively survey consumers’ attitudes and preferences towards this special cake. This can enhance the customer experience when purchasing and enjoying traditional Vietnamese durian cake.

Figure 10: Mean value of the “Attitude toward traditional durian cake” factor

Source: Survey results

Perceived quality impact on attitude towards traditional durian cake: The Perceived Quality factor, measured by four items: Traditional durian cake has a characteristic flavor (CL1); Traditional durian cake has a delicious flavor (CL3); Traditional durian cake has a variety of types (CL4); and Traditional durian cake has a natural origin, safe for health (CL5), were all rated “Agree” by consumers.

This indicates that the perceived quality factor has a significant impact on consumers’ purchasing behavior for traditional durian cake. Nowadays, consumers tend to choose high-quality products that ensure health and have delicious flavors, rather than focusing solely on the price of the product. Consumers are willing to pay a higher price for a product that is of good quality and meets their needs. When consumers perceive that traditional durian cake has high quality, a characteristic and delicious flavor, a variety of types, and that these products are of natural origin and safe for health, they tend to purchase traditional durian cake more frequently.

Consequently, the research team suggests that traditional durian cake craft villages and workshops should actively enhance the quality of traditional durian cake products, diversify designs and flavors, and focus on producing cakes with safe and natural origins, reduced sweetness, and limited use of additives and preservatives to ensure good quality and meet consumer needs, thereby promoting the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake.

Figure 11: Mean value of the “Perceived quality” Factor

Source: Survey results

Perceived price factor: The four measurement items: The price of traditional durian cake is stable in the market (GC1); Traditional durian cake has many price ranges to choose from (GC2); The price of traditional durian cake is suitable for my income (GC3); and The price of traditional durian cake is commensurate with its quality (GC4) were all rated “Agree” by consumers.

This indicates that perceived price has a significant impact on consumers’ purchasing behavior for traditional durian cake. Although consumers prioritize product quality over price, they are willing to pay more for products that offer better quality. However, reasonable pricing is also an important factor that drives purchasing behavior. When consumers perceive that the price of traditional durian cake is stable in the market, offers a variety of price ranges, is suitable for their income, and is commensurate with the cake’s quality, they are more likely to purchase it.

Consequently, the research team suggests several recommendations related to the perceived price factor of traditional durian cake, including creating multiple product segments that cater to consumers’ needs based on income and product quality. Additionally, enhancing promotional activities, developing marketing strategies, and

creating vouchers and discounts can stimulate the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake.

Figure 12: Mean value of the “Perceived price” factor

Source: Survey results

Subjective norms factor: The four measurement items: “People around me buy durian cake (CCQ1); People around me advise me to buy traditional durian cake (CCQ2); There is a lot of information about traditional durian cake on current media (CCQ3); Traditional durian cake is promoted by influential people (CCQ4)” were rated “Neutral” by survey participants. This indicates that subjective norms do not have a significant impact on the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake. It can be observed that the current trend of communication and product promotion is rampant on social media, e-commerce platforms, and newspapers by KOLs and KOCs.

However, considering the characteristics of traditional cakes in general and traditional durian cake in particular, it can be seen that this is a product that should be experienced directly due to its unique flavor and individual taste preferences. Although promotional campaigns for traditional durian cake products may stimulate consumers’ purchase intentions, in terms of purchasing decisions, consumers will rely on other more important factors for evaluation, including quality and price, rather than promotional messages or influence from those around them.

Consequently, the research team suggests that craft villages or KOLs and KOCs who wish to promote traditional durian cake products should focus on related or product-centric stories, as they can significantly impact consumers’ purchase intentions. This should be combined with various quality and product strategies to promote the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers.

Figure 13: Mean value of the “Subjective norms” factor

Source: Survey results

CONCLUSION

Among the four factors considered to directly influence Traditional Durian Cake Purchasing Behavior, three factors at the 5% significance level were found to have an impact on “Traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers”. The Perceived quality (CL) factor has an impact on Attitude towards traditional durian cake (TD) with an impact level of 0.852, indicating that for every one-unit increase in perceived quality, attitude towards durian cake increases by 0.852 units.

Ethnocentrism (TVC) has the largest impact level of 0.518, indicating that for every one-unit increase in ethnocentrism, the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake increases by 0.518 units. Attitude (TD) has an impact level of 0.276 on the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake (HV), indicating that for every one-unit increase in consumer attitude towards traditional durian cake, purchasing behavior increases by 0.276 units.

Perceived Price has an impact level of 0.191 on the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake, indicating that for every one-unit increase in perceived price, purchasing behavior increases by 0.191 units. The Subjective norms (CCQ) factor does not have sufficient statistical significance to conclude about its impact on the dependent variable “Traditional durian cake purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers” (HV).

Consequently, the research team assessed the impact levels of the factors on the purchasing behavior of traditional durian cake and provided recommendations to promote the purchasing behavior of Vietnamese consumers for traditional durian cake products.

References

- 1) Ajzen, I (1991). *The theory of Planned Behavior*. Organizational Behavior and human decision processes, 50, 179-211
- 2) Anh, N. T. V., Tung, H. T., & Linh, D. B. (2022). *Factors Affecting the Intention to Buy Traditional Ao Dai Products: A Case Study of Generation Z in Vietnam*. Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews, 5(4), 111-123.
- 3) Bagozzi, R. and Yi, Y (1988). *On the Evaluation of Structural Equation Models*. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Sciences, 16, 74-94. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02723327>
- 4) Bhasin, H (2023). *Purchase Intention - Role of Purchase Intention in Increasing Sales*. www.marketing91.com/purchase-intention/
- 5) Bhat, Adi (2021). *Consumer Behavior: Definition, Factors and Methods*. QuestionPro, www.questionpro.com/blog/consumer-behavior
- 6) Canh Ky (2019). *What to do to preserve and develop traditional cakes?* <https://tienphong.vn/lam-gi-de-bao-ton-va-phat-trien-banh-dan-gian-post1104781.tpo>
- 7) Chi Quoc (2023). *Can Tho opens the 2023 Southern Folk Cake Festival*. <https://tuoitre.vn/can-tho-khai-mac-le-hoi-banh-dan-gian-nam-bo-nam-2023-20230428194146302.htm>
- 8) Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences (2nd ed.)*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.
- 9) College of Tourism and Hotel (2023). *Summary of 20 traditional Vietnamese cakes, you must know* . <https://saigontourist.edu.vn/cac-loai-banh-co-truyen-viet-nam.html>
- 10) Comrey, A. L., & Lee, H. B. (1992). *A First Course in Factor Analysis (2nd ed.)*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- 11) Devellis, R (2012). *Scale Development Theory and Applications*. Sage Publications, New York.
- 12) Digital Transformation Skill for Vietnamese SMBs (2025). Traditional food business online. <https://nuongbac.com/kinh-doanh-am-thuc-truyen-thong-tren-mang/>
- 13) Dinh Thi Bich Thao (2021). *25 delicious dishes from durian*. <https://www.dienmayxanh.com/vao-bep/sau-rieng-lam-mon-gi-tong-hop-25-mon-ngon-tu-sau-rieng-sieu-10040>
- 14) Dinh Thuong (2019). *Awakening the “market”, “paving the way” for Southern folk cakes*. <https://baophapluat.vn/danh-thuc-thi-truong-mo-duong-cho-banh-dan-gian-nam-bo-post304567.html>
- 15) Do Thi Huong (2021). *Potential for durian development in the provinces of the Southwest region*. Proceedings of the Scientific Workshop: Application of science and technology to enhance the value and sustainable development of durian trees according to the chain in Vietnam. Vietnam Academy of Agriculture
- 16) Doan Huu Trung (2024). *Enhance the value of traditional craft products*. <https://chinhsachcuocsong.vn/vnnet.vn/nang-tam-gia-tri-san-pham-cac-nghe-truyen-thong/33100.html>
- 17) Doanh nghiep (2022). *Developing traditional craft products cannot “swim alone” forever!* <https://laodongthudo.vn/phat-trien-san-pham-nghe-truyen-thong-khong-the-mai-tu-boi-145527.html>
- 18) Fishbein, M & Ajzen, I (1975). *Belief, attitude, intention and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*. Addison- Wesley, Reading, MA
- 19) Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) (1st ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage publications.

- 20) Hoang Manh Cuong, et al., (2021). *Overview of the production and consumption of durian products in Vietnam and some countries in the region. Proceedings of the Scientific Conference: Application of science and technology to enhance the value and sustainable development of durian trees according to the chain in Vietnam.* Vietnam Academy of Agriculture.
- 21) Hoang Trong & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc (2008). *Analysis of research data with SPSS – 2 volumes.* Hong Duc Publishing House, HCM city.
- 22) Hock, C., Ringle, C.M., & Sarstedt, M (2010). *Management of multi-purpose stadiums: Importance and performance measurement of service interfaces.* International Journal of Services Technology and Management, 14(2-3)
- 23) Hong Dang (2019). *Why Southern folk cakes do not have a large consumer market?* <https://www.qdnd.vn/kinh-te/cac-van-de/vi-sao-banh-dan-gian-nam-bo-chua-co-thi-truong-tieu-thu-rong-lon-571626>
- 24) Hong Nhung (2023). *International newspapers suggest delicious traditional Vietnamese cakes.* <https://afamily.vn/bao-quoc-te/goi-y-nhung-mon-banh-truyen-thong-thom-ngon-cua-viet-nam-20230714163027528.chn>
- 25) Hu, L. & Bentler, P. (1999). *Cutoff criteria for fit indices in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives.* Structural Equation Modeling, 6(1), 1-55
- 26) Khanh Duy (2024). *Delicious durian crepe flavor.* <https://baocaobang.vn/thom-ngon-huong-vi-banh-crepe-sau-rieng-3170866.html>
- 27) Klein, J. G., Ettenson, R., & Morris, M. D. (1998). *The Animosity Model of Foreign Product Purchase: An Empirical Test in the People's Republic of China.* Journal of Marketing, 62 (Jan-1998), 89-100.
- 28) Lam Ngoc Thuy (2021). *Intention to buy domestic fashion products: Research results of Generation Z group in Lam Dong.* Journal of Banking Science & Training
- 29) Le Nguyen Hau, Tran Truc Quynh, Le Duc Anh (2011). *"Vietnamese people use Vietnamese goods": The role of ethnocentrism and evaluation on the willingness to buy Vietnamese goods.* Science & Technology Development, Vol 14, No. Q3- 2011, 56-67
- 30) MBA Skool Team (2021). *Purchase Intention Definition | Marketing Dictionary | MBA Skool-Study. Learn. Share.* www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/marketing-and-strategy-terms/10976-purchase-intention.html
- 31) Ngo Thi Khue Thu (2015). *Ethnocentrism of youth in the Central market.* Journal of Science and Technology, University of Danang, 4(89), 30-34.
- 32) Nguyen Bao Ngoc (2019). *Ethnocentrism in consumption and factors affecting the intention to consume domestic products.* Journal of financial and accounting research, No. 04(189).
- 33) Nguyen Ngan (2023). *Food businesses have a wide range of export opportunities.* <https://baodautu.vn/doanh-nghiep-thuc-pham-rong-duong-xuat-khau-d202126.html>
- 34) Nguyen Thi Van Anh, et al., (2022). *Factors Affecting the Intention to Buy Traditional Ao Dai Products: A Case Study of Generation Z in Vietnam.* Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews, ISSN 2775-9237, DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.05.04.463
- 35) Pham Thi Be Loan, Bui Thanh Huan (2012). *Ethnocentrism, perceived value, domestic product trust and consumer behavioral intention towards domestically produced children's supplements.* Collection of Reports of the 8th Scientific Research Student Conference, Danang University, 2012
- 36) Phan Thanh Nam & Ngo Chi Thanh (2024). *Factors affecting the purchasing behavior of domestic confectionery of Vietnamese people.* Hong Duc University Science Journal, No. 70.2024, 97-106.

- 37) Phan Trung Nam (2013). *Research on factors affecting the intention to buy Vietnamese children's clothes in Ho Chi Minh city*. Master thesis in economics. University of Economics Ho Chi Minh
- 38) Quang Vũ (2024). *Bánh sầu riêng 9 Sạch đưa Hương vị Việt tới thị trường quốc tế*. <https://kenh14.vn/banh-sau-rieng-9-sach-dua-huong-vi-viet-toi-thi-truong-quoc-te-20240116121858706.chn>
- 39) Radu. V (2023). *Consumer Behavior in Marketing - Patterns, Types, Segmentation*. *Omniconvert Ecommerce Growth Blog*. www.omniconvert.com/blog/consumer-behavior-in-marketing-patterns-types-segmentation/
- 40) SGTT Online Reporter Group (2019). *What market for traditional cakes?* <https://thesaigontimes.vn/thi-truong-nao-cho-banh-dan-gian/>
- 41) Shimp. T. A, & Sharma. S (1987). *Consumer Ethnocentrism: Construction and Validation of the CETSCALE*. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 24(3), 280-289.
- 42) Sumner. G. A (1906). *Folkways*. New York: Ginn Custom.
- 43) Tam An (2024). *Earning 16,850 billion/month, durian is in season all over the world, price skyrocketing*. <https://vietnamnet.vn/sau-rieng-vao-mua-ca-the-gioi-chi-viet-nam-co-gia-cao-cho-vot-2342424.html>
- 44) tapchicongthuong.vn (2023). *Soc Trang: Increasing capacity for pia cake and Chinese sausage production through the national industrial promotion group project*. <https://tapchicongthuong.vn/soc-trang-tang-nang-luc-cho-san-xuat-banh-pia-lap-xuong-qua-de-an-nhom-khuyen-cong-quoc-gia-108705.htm>
- 45) Thanh Tuyen (2025). *"Vietnamese Cake" position and development in the current market*. <https://daylambanh.edu.vn/su-phat-trien-cua-banh-viet-hien-nay>
- 46) Tran Kim Dung (2015). *Research on the influence of ethnocentrism on consumers' intention to buy domestic products - the case of confectionery products in Da Nang city market*. Master's thesis in Business Administration. Da Nang University
- 47) Tran Thi Tuan Anh, et al., (2023). *Factors affecting consumers' intention and behavior to purchase powdered milk - the moderating role of ethnocentrism*. *Journal of Economic Science*, 11(01), pp.68-86.
- 48) Tuong Vy (2019). *Discover traditional cakes at the "country markets" of Mo Cay Nam*. https://bentretourism.vn/vi/detailnews/?t=exploring-traditional-cake-cuisine-at-rural-markets-in-mo-cay-nam&id=news_2506
- 49) Visa. I, Faihurst. A (1999). *Factors underlying the phenomenon of consumer ethnocentricity: evidence from four central European countries*. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 9(4). 321-337, <http://doi.org/10.1080/095939699342444>
- 50) Vuong Quoc Duy (2014). *Factors affecting the consumption of Pia cake in Soc Trang*. *Can Tho University Journal of Science*, 33(2014), 109-118.
- 51) Xuan Mai (2023). *Traditional foods: Big market, Small interest*. <https://tuoitre.vn/thuc-pham-truyen-thong-thi-truong-lon-quan-tam-nho-2023092407551002.htm>